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Transformation of Madrasah Management: Strategy to Increase Public Trust in State Elementary Madrasah 1 Grobogan

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Abstract

The transformation of Islamic education management is very important in increasing the competitiveness of madrasahs in the era of public school dominance, especially in areas with a strong santri culture. The purpose of this research is to analyze how madrasahs transform to increase public trust. By using a qualitative approach with a case study design, data were collected through interviews, observations, and documentation studies. The research found that MIN 1 Grobogan successfully implemented a management transformation strategy to increase public trust through several strategic steps. First, the madrasah focuses on building an innovative and quality image, promoting superior academic and non-academic programs. Second, transparent fund management and accountability in its use create public trust. Third, friendly and professional service by staff is an advantage. Improving the quality of teachers through continuous training and the use of information technology in learning is also prioritized. In addition, the integration of religious values and social skills through daily programs, as well as cooperation with local communities, is the key to improving student character. However, although this strategy was successful, this transformation also faced challenges in adapting educators and budget limitations for facility development. These findings provide an important contribution to understanding the dynamics of education management in madrasahs.

Keywords: Madrasah Transformation, Educational Management, Public Trust, Competitiveness, Educational Innovation

1. Introduction

Islamic education in Indonesia currently faces significant challenges amidst dynamic social changes and rapid technological developments. One surprising social fact is the low public interest in Islamic educational institutions, including madrasahs, even in areas with strong santri communities (Bakar, 2015; Lestari & Masyithoh, 2023; Rahman & Akbar, 2021). For example, MIN 1 Grobogan, located in Kuwaron Village, Gubug, Grobogan, Central Java, experienced a decline in the number of students, even though it is located in an environment where the majority of the community identifies with the santri culture. Furthermore, data from the Indonesian Ministry of

Religion (Kementerian Agama RI, 2020) shows that although the number of madrasahs in Indonesia is increasing, their attractiveness and quality are still often perceived as lower than in public schools. This phenomenon raises questions about the effectiveness of Islamic education management in meeting the expectations of society in the modern era, and the extent to which these institutions are able to compete with public schools in an increasingly competitive environment.

The literature highlights the significant potential of Islamic education, including madrasahs, in fostering character development and promoting Islamic values (Tholkhah, 1998). Then Tayeb (2018) emphasized that Islamic education in Southeast Asia, particularly in Indonesia, requires innovation in management and curriculum to remain relevant and address contemporary needs. Similarly, Subroto et al. (2023) and Umar (2015) identified innovation in madrasah management strategies and the integration of technology as critical factors in enhancing the attractiveness and competitiveness of Islamic educational institutions in meeting modern societal expectations. Meanwhile, Nata (2016) further noted that one of the reasons for the declining popularity of madrasahs is their limited ability to adapt to changing times, particularly in management practices. This review underscores that innovative management, which integrates Islamic values with modern competencies such as information technology and foreign languages, offers a promising solution to the challenges confronting madrasahs.

The purpose of this research is to analyze the management transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan as an effort to increase the attractiveness and trust of the community. By exploring the innovative steps taken by MIN 1 Grobogan, such as updates in the learning system, strengthening Islamic values through daily activities, and implementing effective marketing strategies, this research is expected to describe the real impact of adaptive management on public perception and student interest. This research also aims to contribute to the development of Islamic education management theory, focusing on how the combination of religious approaches and modern skills can create relevant and competitive madrasahs. Umar (2015) shows that the adaptation of madrasah management that is not responsive to changes in the times becomes the main cause of the lack of attractiveness of madrasahs from the perspective of the community.

Based on the above background, the implementation of innovative and adaptive management strategies at MIN 1 Grobogan can increase the attractiveness and public trust in madrasahs, as explained by Umar (Umar, 2014). Then Ridwan & Maryati (2024) stated that Islamic education that is responsive to the demands of the times has the potential to expand its scope and relevance among modern society. Therefore, this research argues that the combination of strong religious values and modern skills, such as foreign language skills and digital literacy, can be an effective model for other madrasahs in Indonesia to maintain their competitiveness in today's educational world.

2. Literature Review

In order to understand the management transformation that occurred at MIN 1 Grobogan, this literature review divides the focus of the research into two main aspects: material objects and formal objects. Material objects in this research refer to concrete elements that are changed in madrasah management to increase public appeal and trust, such as changes in curriculum, uniforms, and strengthening Islamic identity in the madrasah environment. According to Azra (2001), the global challenges faced by Islamic education, especially in Southeast Asia, require madrasahs to adapt to innovations in various fields. MIN 1 Grobogan, as one of the Islamic educational institutions in an area with a strong santri culture, presents an important case study on how concrete changes in management can have a significant effect on the image and competitiveness of madrasahs amidst the dominance of public schools. The efforts to transform madrasah include innovations in information technology-based learning and strengthening foreign language skills that show a response to the needs of modern education.

On the other hand, the formal object of this research is the Islamic education management approach itself, which is the conceptual framework for understanding transformation strategies. This formal approach involves a review of literature on innovative management in Islamic education, as described by Nata (2003) who emphasizes the importance of the role of adaptive management to ensure the competitiveness of madrasahs in the broader educational context. Improving the quality of teaching staff, learning facilities, and marketing strategies are

management elements that are considered capable of developing a positive image of the institution. In the context of MIN 1 Grobogan, the implementation of intensive marketing strategies, the introduction of daily religious activities, and the implementation of regular and uniform study hours are some real examples of the application of responsive education management concepts. With a structured education management approach, MIN 1 Grobogan is able to strengthen its position as a superior madrasah that is in demand by the community.

This literature review highlights that the combination of material innovation and the application of formal approaches in educational management is the key to the success of the transformation at MIN Kuwaron. The support from the local government and active participation from stakeholders have accelerated the process of adaptation and management renewal at this madrasah. Through a material and formal perspective, this research positions MIN 1 Grobogan as an example of successful madrasah management transformation, showing that the application of strong Islamic values can be in line with technological innovation and the needs of modern education. This success not only makes a positive contribution to increasing the number of students, but also strengthens the role of madrasahs in providing quality education that is in accordance with the development of the times and the needs of society.

3. Research Method

This research focuses on the transformation of madrasah management and increasing public trust in MIN 1 Grobogan. The main objective is to explore the impact of management changes and public perceptions of the educational institution. Using a qualitative approach with a case study design, this research is expected to provide a deep understanding of the dynamics that occur in the context of madrasah management.

In this research, the main variable is the transformation of madrasah management which is operationalized through indicators to measure the success of management transformation, such as (1) image development (2) innovative, (3) transparent fund management, (4) staff professionalism, (5) improving the teacher quality, (6) integration of religious values and social skills, and (7) cooperation with local communities. Meanwhile, the public trust variable is measured by indicators (1) community satisfaction, (2) openness of information, (3) community support, and (4) positive perceptions of the quality of education in madrasahs.

Then the main data collection technique was carried out through in-depth interviews with the head of the madrasah, teachers, committees, and parents as many as seven people who were given the initials MIG 1 to MIG 7, to explore their experiences, views, and expectations regarding the management policies implemented. Thus, this research does not only rely on quantitative data, but also considers the subjective perspectives of teachers who have direct experience (Gammelgaard, 2017). In addition, direct observation was carried out to obtain a holistic picture of management practices in the madrasah and its contribution to increasing public trust. Documentation studies were used to enrich the data and provide historical context related to the development of the madrasah, which allows for a deeper understanding of the management transformation process that occurred (Houghton et al., 2015).

After the data is collected, the next step is to analyze the data using the Miles and Huberman model, which includes the stages of data collection, reduction, presentation, and drawing conclusions (Miles et al., 2018). This method was chosen because of its ability to process qualitative data systematically, in-depth, and relevant to the research objectives. In addition, to maintain data validity, this research uses triangulation by comparing information from interviews, observations, and documentation. The member-checking process is carried out by asking for confirmation from informants regarding initial findings, ensuring that data interpretation reflects real conditions in the field.

With this approach, this research is expected to provide useful insights into the contribution of madrasah management transformation to increasing public trust (Safarudin et al., 2023), as well as offer practical recommendations for more effective managerial strategies in developing education in madrasahs.

This research examines the transformation of madrasah management and its role in increasing public trust at MIN 1 Grobogan. The primary objective is to explore the impact of management changes on public perceptions of this

educational institution. Utilizing a qualitative approach with a case study design, this study aims to provide an in-depth understanding of the dynamics involved in madrasah management transformation. The main variable in this research is the transformation of madrasah management, operationalized through several indicators to measure its success: (1) image development, (2) innovation, (3) transparent financial management, (4) staff professionalism, (5) teacher quality improvement, (6) integration of religious values and social skills, and (7) collaboration with local communities. The public trust variable, on the other hand, is assessed through indicators such as (1) community satisfaction, (2) information transparency, (3) community support, and (4) positive perceptions of the quality of madrasah education.

The primary data collection technique involved in-depth interviews with the head of the madrasah, teachers, committee members, and parents—seven individuals in total—who were assigned the initials MIG 1 to MIG 7. These interviews aimed to explore their experiences, perspectives, and expectations regarding the implemented management policies. Consequently, this research does not solely rely on quantitative data but also incorporates the subjective perspectives of individuals with direct experience, particularly teachers (Gammelgaard, 2017). Additionally, direct observations were conducted to obtain a holistic understanding of management practices within the madrasah and their role in fostering public trust. Documentation analysis was also employed to enrich the data and provide historical context about the madrasah's development. This approach allowed for a more comprehensive understanding of the management transformation process (Houghton et al., 2015).

After data collection, the next step was data analysis using the Miles and Huberman model, which comprises four stages: data collection, reduction, presentation, and conclusion drawing (Miles et al., 2018). This method was selected for its systematic and in-depth approach to processing qualitative data, ensuring alignment with the research objectives.

To enhance data validity, triangulation was employed by comparing information obtained from interviews, observations, and documentation. Additionally, member checking was conducted by seeking confirmation from informants regarding preliminary findings, ensuring that data interpretations accurately reflect field conditions. Through this approach, the research aims to provide valuable insights into the contribution of madrasah management transformation in fostering public trust (Safarudin et al., 2023). It also seeks to offer practical recommendations for implementing more effective managerial strategies to advance education in madrasahs.

4. Research Result

4.1. Madrasah management transformation strategy to increase public trust

This research identified that the transformation of madrasah management at MIN 1 Grobogan, aimed at increasing public trust, was accomplished through various strategic initiatives. First, the madrasah prioritized building an innovative and high-quality image by promoting superior programs in both academic and non-academic domains, effectively attracting public interest and confidence in entrusting their children's education. Second, transparent financial management became a cornerstone of trust-building efforts. This transparency was reinforced by the madrasah's commitment to enhanced accountability in the use of operational funds. Third, friendly and professional service emerged as a key strength. The madrasah ensured that its staff consistently delivered excellent service to students and their guardians.

Additionally, improving the quality of teachers and educational staff was a priority. Continuous professional development programs were implemented to enhance their competencies, particularly in leveraging relevant information technology in teaching and learning activities. The madrasah also implemented a daily habituation program that integrates religious values and social skills, enabling students to excel academically while developing strong moral character. Finally, collaboration with the local community was strengthened to enhance learning quality. The madrasah actively involved parents and community leaders in various activities, fostering a sense of shared responsibility. Collectively, these strategies have successfully positioned MIN 1 Grobogan as a transparent, innovative, and high-quality educational institution, significantly increasing public trust.

4.2. Improving the Quality of Learning

MIN 1 Grobogan demonstrates a strong commitment to building public trust through the provision of quality and innovative learning. One of the key strategic initiatives is updating the curriculum to align with contemporary demands, particularly in fostering technology skills. As noted by informant MIG1, *“Students’ IT skills are very good because the learning is IT-based, including exams,”* highlighting the importance of integrating technology into the curriculum. Additionally, the madrasah offers an English language interest program every Saturday, facilitated by alumni from the English department. This initiative was acknowledged by MIG3, who stated, *“The habituation of foreign languages is still ongoing, even English is one of the interest groups.”* These efforts are further complemented by religious programs, such as the daily habituation of *Asmaul Husna* and the *Dhuha* prayer each morning. As emphasized by MIG5, *“This religious habituation continues to be maintained as part of the madrasah’s identity,”* underscoring the prioritization of religious values. Through these various innovations, MIN 1 Grobogan has successfully created a learning environment that excels in academics, technology integration, and religious values. This holistic approach has attracted parents from diverse backgrounds, further solidifying the madrasah’s reputation as a trusted and quality educational institution.

Another notable transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan is the renewal of the learning system and student uniform regulations, aimed at fostering a disciplined and consistent Islamic environment. The principal introduced changes to the uniform policy, mandating headscarves and long clothing for female students and long pants for male students, reflecting Islamic values. As noted by MIG2, *“This change in uniform is in accordance with Islamic teachings and provides a strong identity.”* This uniform adjustment was complemented by a more structured reorganization of the learning schedule, ensuring uniform entry and exit times for all students. MIG4 highlighted the impact of this change, stating, *“Now the children study more regularly.”* These initiatives send a clear message to the community that MIN 1 Grobogan is committed to instilling discipline and Islamic values. The findings of this research indicate that such changes have successfully attracted community interest, particularly among parents seeking an educational environment that prioritizes Islamic principles for their children’s development.

This aligns with the results of observations conducted on August 29, 2024, which highlighted significant changes in the learning system and the enforcement of student uniform regulations at MIN 1 Grobogan. These observations underscore the principal’s initiative in fostering a disciplined environment consistent with Islamic values. One of the most notable changes is the implementation of a new uniform policy, requiring female students to wear the hijab and modest long clothing, while male students wear long pants. This policy not only reflects adherence to Islamic teachings but also instills a strong identity among students, fostering a sense of pride and attachment to religious values. Additionally, the study schedule was reorganized to be more structured, with standardized entry and exit times for all students. Observations revealed that students appeared more focused and orderly during the teaching and learning process, reflecting the positive impact of these changes. These efforts convey a clear message to the community that MIN 1 Grobogan is committed to cultivating discipline and reinforcing Islamic principles. The strong support from parents and the wider community for these policies highlights their aspirations for quality, religion-based education that nurtures both academic excellence and moral character in their children.

In addition to reforms in the learning system, MIN 1 Grobogan places significant emphasis on strengthening Islamic culture through daily religious activities. Every morning, students and teachers begin their day by reciting *Asmaul Husna* and the Qur’an, followed by congregational prayers during the day. MIG3 noted, *“This brings students closer to the Qur’an every day.”* The program also includes the recitation of Surah Yassin every Friday, which not only reinforces students’ religious values but also fosters a sense of togetherness within the madrasah. MIG7 highlighted, *“The program of reading Surah Yassin is a characteristic of our madrasah,”* emphasizing its positive impact on the religious atmosphere of the institution.

This series of religious activities has drawn significant attention from the surrounding community, distinguishing MIN 1 Grobogan as a unique alternative to public schools. Its strong emphasis on Islamic values has successfully appealed to parents seeking an education system that seamlessly integrates academic excellence with a solid foundation in religious principles.

4.3. Budget transparency and increased cooperation with local communities

MIN 1 Grobogan has implemented a strategy of transparency as part of its effort to build trust with the community and parents. The principal emphasized the importance of openness in reporting both the madrasah's programs and the use of its funds. MIG4 noted, *"To maintain public trust, madrasah programs must be transparent, including infrastructure development."* This transparency is further reinforced through the involvement of the school committee, which plays a key role in monitoring and evaluating the performance of the madrasah. In addition, regular reports on academic achievements and outstanding programs are provided to parents. MIG1 added, *"Parents can monitor their children's development, especially in the tahfidz program, which is divided into seven halaqoh."* This enables parents to directly assess their children's progress while strengthening trust in the quality of education. MIG3 emphasized, *"We are given space to participate in the education process,"* further strengthening the relationship between the madrasah and the community through this openness.

In addition to transparency, MIN 1 Grobogan fosters trust through active cooperation with the surrounding community. Through its harmonious relationship with the local population, MIN 1 Grobogan has expanded its student base from one village to eight sub-districts. MIG2 remarked, *"Previously, students were only from one neighborhood association or a maximum of one village; now students come from eight sub-districts,"* reflecting the increased public trust. The madrasah's involvement in various social and religious activities further strengthens its presence within the community. MIG4 stated, *"The majority of MIN alumni continue to MTsN and favorite junior high schools in Grobogan,"* indicating that the madrasah is recognized for its high-quality education. This close cooperation underscores MIN 1 Grobogan's commitment to creating a positive impact within the community, as MIG1 emphasized, *"This good relationship has proven effective in maintaining public trust."*

In line with the above, observations on August 29, 2024, revealed that the atmosphere at MIN 1 Grobogan was lively and dynamic, reflecting the success of the madrasah in building trust through active collaboration with the community. In the schoolyard, children joyfully played traditional games, laughing, while teachers engaged in warm discussions with parents present to support the school's activities. Colorful banners promoting social and educational initiatives decorated the area, signaling the madrasah's participation in various community-centered projects. The presence of students from eight sub-districts demonstrated that MIN 1 Grobogan had expanded its reach, attracting interest from a broader community that once was limited to a single village. Religious activities, such as study sessions and social services, were frequently conducted in the surrounding area, further deepening the harmonious relationship between the madrasah and the local community. Alumni were seen actively continuing their studies at popular MTsN and junior high schools, reaffirming MIN 1 Grobogan's reputation as a quality educational institution. Through its ongoing activities involving parents and the community, the madrasah's presence among residents has become more prominent, showcasing its strong commitment to creating a positive impact and reinforcing the bonds of trust in the area. This environment fosters a warm, familial atmosphere, where all parties contribute to creating a supportive and enthusiastic learning space.

The implementation of MIN 1 Grobogan's transparency and collaboration strategy continues to enhance the institution's positive image as a responsible educational entity. The principal prioritizes openness in managing funds and actively involves external parties in evaluating ongoing programs. MIG3 noted, *"Transparency is important so that the community trusts the management of the madrasah."* The madrasah regularly holds meetings with parents to provide updates on program progress, such as the tahfidz program, which is divided into several halaqoh groups, a practice that is well-received by guardians. MIG5 added, *"This openness is beneficial because we, as parents, can see the quality of the program our children are participating in."* By maintaining a strong commitment to transparency, the madrasah has reinforced its position as an institution that prioritizes the quality and sustainability of education. As MIG7 concluded, *"The transparency of this madrasah makes us increasingly confident in entrusting our children's education here."*

4.4. Daily habituation program, foreign language, and IT

MIN 1 Grobogan has developed a daily habituation program that has become a significant draw for the Grobogan community, focusing on religious activities such as reciting Asmaul Husna, dhuha prayer, and tahfidz. The tahfidz program is divided into seven halaqoh, with each group guided by asatidz hufadz. As MIG5 mentioned, *"The*

students who take tahfidz are divided into seven halaqoh and are taught by asatidz hufadz.” For students who have not yet joined the tahfidz program, they receive guidance on memorizing short surahs as preparation. MIG2 explained, *“The tasmi’ activity or tahfidz exam is a long-awaited moment, including preparation for the tahfidz graduation at the end of the year.”* This structured and consistent religious program is seen as instrumental in helping students develop strong character. MIG3 stated, *“This daily habituation is very helpful for students in developing disciplined and religious character.”* The positive impact of this program is evident in MIG1’s observation that, *“The religious atmosphere created makes this madrasah increasingly seen as the community’s top choice.”*

In addition to religious programs, MIN 1 Grobogan emphasizes the development of students' competencies in foreign languages and information technology to meet modern demands. Arabic and English are introduced from the first grade, supported by the extracurricular activity "English Arabic Speaking Club," which is designed to enhance students' speaking skills. The school has also established computer and language laboratories, providing essential facilities for digital learning. MIG4 noted, *“The computer and language laboratory facilities offer students access to technology from an early age.”* MIG5 added, *“Students’ ability to speak foreign languages also improves through the club activities that are regularly held.”* As MIG2 emphasized, the integration of technology *“increases students’ competitiveness and prepares the school to face global challenges.”* MIG3 further remarked, *“The role of technology has made the madrasah more popular and seen as a progressive institution.”*

On August 29, 2024, the atmosphere at MIN 1 Grobogan was observed to be lively and full of enthusiasm. Students were seen eagerly entering the classroom, carrying English and Arabic books, their faces bright with smiles. Inside the classroom, teachers energetically introduced new vocabulary in both languages, while students actively participated by answering questions and engaging in discussions. Outside the classroom, the extracurricular activity "English Arabic Speaking Club" was in full swing. Students gathered in small groups, practicing speaking and helping each other with pronunciation. The sound of laughter and conversation in both English and Arabic filled the air, creating an enjoyable and supportive language-learning environment. Meanwhile, the computer and language labs were bustling with students exploring technology. Modern computers, equipped with educational software, were in use, and several students worked collaboratively on projects, showcasing strong teamwork. Teachers attentively supervised, providing guidance when needed. The overall atmosphere reflected the madrasah’s commitment to preparing students to face global challenges with essential language and technology skills. MIN 1 Grobogan has succeeded in fostering a progressive learning environment where students gain not only academic knowledge but also the skills they need for the future.

MIN 1 Grobogan’s innovative programs have earned it a strong reputation as an educational institution that not only emphasizes religious values but also prioritizes the development of skills aligned with the demands of the digital era. MIG1 noted, *“This madrasah is indeed well-known in the community because of its comprehensive programs.”* Public trust in MIN 1 Grobogan continues to grow, as highlighted by MIG4, who stated, *“This madrasah offers a well-rounded education that combines religious teachings with modern skills.”* MIG7 further emphasized, *“The madrasah is the first choice for parents who want their children to grow with both religious integrity and competitive skills.”* According to MIG2, *“MIN 1 Grobogan’s reputation for adapting to the times makes it the top choice for education in this region.”* This growing public trust affirms that the madrasah’s innovative approach meets the needs and expectations of modern education while reinforcing its status as a leading institution in a competitive educational landscape.

4.5. Strengthening the Quality of Teachers and Education Personnel

MIN 1 Grobogan is deeply committed to enhancing the quality of its teaching staff in order to maintain public trust and improve educational standards. Through regular training, the school encourages teachers to adopt innovative and relevant teaching methods. *“Teachers are given training to continuously update their teaching methods in line with current developments,”* said MIG4, reflecting the school’s focus on educational advancement. The school also implements a task division based on teacher competency to ensure that students receive optimal guidance. MIG5 explained, *“Our tahfidz teachers are asatidz hufadz who are highly competent,”* illustrating the school’s emphasis on competency-based learning. As a result, MIN 1 Grobogan has successfully integrated

technology-based learning and prioritized teaching quality. “Strengthening teacher quality is key to maintaining high educational standards,” added MIG1, underscoring the importance of educator quality in preserving the school’s strong reputation within the community.

MIN 1 Grobogan also places significant emphasis on pedagogical development through ongoing efforts to enhance teacher skills. Routine training is conducted to equip teachers with the latest technological advancements and teaching methods. MIG3 stated, “This training really helps teachers to be more innovative in teaching,” emphasizing the school’s role in supporting the professional growth of educators. The division of tasks based on each teacher’s area of expertise is another key aspect of this strategy, as MIG7 explained, “Each teacher has responsibilities according to their expertise, ensuring that students can learn optimally.” This focus on improving teacher quality not only helps enhance the effectiveness of learning but also strengthens public trust in MIN 1 Grobogan. MIG2 noted, “Good teacher quality assures parents that their children are receiving a quality education.”

The atmosphere at MIN 1 Grobogan on August 29, 2024, reflected the school’s commitment to enhancing the quality of education. In the morning, teachers gathered in a well-equipped training room, surrounded by modern teaching tools that showcased the school’s embrace of technological advancements. The teachers’ faces were filled with enthusiasm as they engaged in discussions, shared experiences, and learned about the latest teaching methods. The training session fostered a warm and collaborative environment, with teachers actively participating in the Q&A session, further enhancing the spirit of cooperation. The clear division of tasks according to each teacher’s area of expertise ensured that everyone was focused on delivering quality content. In the classrooms, the sound of joyful children learning echoed throughout, illustrating the positive outcomes of these professional development efforts. The lively interaction between teachers and students not only improved the students’ learning experiences but also instilled a sense of confidence and pride in the teachers. Furthermore, parents who attended the event to witness the activities expressed their support for the school’s initiatives to elevate educational quality. Overall, the atmosphere at MIN 1 Grobogan on that day demonstrated a high level of dedication to creating a quality, progressive, and dynamic learning environment.

Through various capacity-building programs, MIN 1 Grobogan demonstrates a holistic approach to fostering an innovative and high-quality educational environment. The school’s commitment to equipping teachers with the skills to adapt to educational changes is evident in its ongoing training initiatives. As MIG4 expressed, “With this training, we are better prepared to face changes in the world of education.” The strategic division of tasks based on teacher specialization further enhances the school’s success. MIG5 highlighted, “Our tahfidz teachers are the best in their fields,” underscoring the school’s dedication to providing top-tier instruction. Additionally, MIN 1 Grobogan actively encourages the integration of technology into the teaching process, recognizing its role in improving learning efficiency. MIG3 emphasized, “Technological innovation in schools greatly helps student learning,” reflecting the school’s commitment to using modern tools to support education. This focus on both teacher development and technological advancement has helped MIN 1 Grobogan gain recognition as a trusted and quality educational institution within the community.

4.6. Friendly and Professional Service

MIN 1 Grobogan has earned a positive reputation due to its friendly and professional service, which has become a significant draw for the surrounding community. The school’s principal and staff are committed to establishing harmonious relationships with parents and students, ensuring that everyone is treated with respect and care. MIG1 emphasized, “Friendly service makes parents feel appreciated and comfortable.” This approach extends to effectively handling complaints and suggestions from parents, ensuring their concerns are addressed in a timely and thoughtful manner. MIG3 added, “The principal is always open to criticism, which makes us feel closer.” The school also conducts regular evaluations of its service system to ensure it meets community expectations. MIG5 noted, “We always listen to the input from parents as a form of commitment to improving the quality of education.” With this responsive and open approach, MIN 1 Grobogan has built strong relationships with the community, earning increasing public trust.

On August 31, 2024, the school was alive with the sound of intimate conversations between parents and staff, demonstrating the close relationship between the school and families. The principal, with a friendly smile, often approached parents, welcoming their opinions. These conversations reflected the school's openness to feedback, making parents feel valued and involved in their children's education. The waiting area in the madrasah office was filled with educational magazines and information, showcasing the staff's efforts to provide informative services. Organized bulletin boards offered clear and accessible information to parents, reinforcing the school's commitment to transparency. Throughout the area, staff members were alert and ready to assist with any questions, creating a comfortable and professional atmosphere. Overall, MIN 1 Grobogan is more than a place of learning; it is a community where individuals feel valued and actively involved in the educational process.

In addition to its services, MIN 1 Grobogan's management innovation plays a key role in shaping a positive image of the madrasah. The school's excellent programs—both academic and non-academic—along with its consistent religious practices, are particularly attractive. MIG2 shared, "Previously, students were only from one neighborhood association or village, now they are from eight sub-districts." This innovation not only increases enrollment but also ensures the quality of education remains high. MIG4 noted, "Our teachers always take training to continue updating teaching methods." These programs also promote student success in both academic and religious areas, reinforcing MIN 1 Grobogan's reputation as a trusted and high-quality madrasah.

Another factor contributing to the school's success is the commitment of the teaching staff to continually enhance their competencies. Teachers actively participate in training, workshops, and seminars to stay up-to-date with the latest teaching methods. MIG5 explained, "Improving the quality of teachers is our priority so that students obtain the best learning." The full support from management in providing resources and facilities has a positive impact on both teachers and students. MIG7 emphasized, "With complete facilities, the teaching and learning process becomes more effective." The strong collaboration between management, teachers, and the community is a key factor in the school's ongoing development and success.

MIN 1 Grobogan continues to innovate by offering various excellent programs across both academic and non-academic fields. Students participate in local and national competitions, which helps them develop their skills and boost their self-confidence. MIG3 mentioned, "We participate in various academic and non-academic competitions as an effort to improve student achievement." The structured tahfidz program is also a key advantage of the school. MIG5 explained, "The tahfidz program is divided into several levels to ensure that each student develops according to their abilities." Community support for this program is robust, with MIG2 adding, "With this program, our children are ready to continue to a higher level." Thanks to its success in both academic and non-academic areas, MIN 1 Grobogan continues to earn the community's trust as an institution that produces high-achieving and well-rounded generations.

4.7. Challenges in implementing madrasah management transformation strategies and increasing public trust

The transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan faced several significant challenges, especially in terms of adapting educators to the new system that requires additional skills. Some teachers still need training to utilize the technology optimally, especially in the use of computer labs. MIG1 said, "We still have difficulty operating some of the devices in the lab, so training is very necessary." MIG2 added that this challenge is not just about technology, but also about skills in teaching foreign languages, which are also part of this transformation. MIG3 stated, "Without further training, it is difficult for us to keep up with the developments needed." This opinion was reinforced by MIG4, who said that the success of the management transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan would depend greatly on the readiness of educators to implement changes comprehensively. Therefore, ongoing training is an important aspect that needs to be considered by the madrasah so that educators are ready to provide optimal education.

In addition, budget constraints also pose a challenge in developing adequate learning facilities at MIN 1 Grobogan. Although there is support from the Ministry of Religious Affairs, the need for more sophisticated equipment is still difficult to meet. MIG5 admitted, "The existing budget is not enough to buy the sophisticated devices we

need.” MIG7 added, “Some computers are old and require expensive maintenance.” According to MIG2, maintaining these facilities often burdens the limited budget, so further support is needed. MIG4 also emphasized that support from the government, community, and other stakeholders will greatly assist the sustainability of this transformation. This challenge shows the importance of collaboration from various parties to ensure that the transformation of MIN 1 Grobogan can continue and develop in order to improve the quality of education.

The management transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan has had a significant impact on both the madrasah itself and the Islamic education system in Indonesia in general. The success of MIN 1 Grobogan in attracting public interest through management innovation shows that madrasahs can be an alternative to high-quality education compared to public schools. According to MIG1, “MIN 1 Grobogan proves that with innovation, madrasahs can attract more students.” The consistent strengthening of Islamic values, accompanied by modern skills, makes MIN 1 Grobogan a model for other madrasahs. MIG2 stated, “This new approach has increased public trust in madrasahs.” Thus, this transformation serves as an inspiration for other Islamic educational institutions to adopt similar strategies to increase their competitiveness. This is also reinforced by MIG4, who emphasized, “Innovation in management is very important to improve the quality of education in madrasahs.” It can be said that MIN 1 Grobogan has created a new paradigm that proves that madrasahs have the potential to compete in the wider world of education.

From an educational management perspective, the transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan shows that adaptation to the needs of the times can be achieved without neglecting religious values. According to MIG3, “The combination of religious activities with 21st-century skills is the key to the success of madrasahs.” By combining religious lessons and skills such as foreign languages and technology, MIN 1 Grobogan has succeeded in creating an Islamic education model that is relevant to the demands of globalization. MIG5 added, “A holistic education creates graduates who are ready to face global challenges.” This implication suggests that madrasah development requires changes not only in teaching methods but also innovations in governance. MIG7 commented, “Modern facilities and relevant methods are essential to meet the expectations of today’s society.” Thus, the management transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan has not only brought about changes in teaching, but also strengthened the position of madrasahs as educational institutions that are ready to compete in the modern era.

Finally, the transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan has positive implications for the development of Islamic education policies at the regional and national levels. The success of this madrasah in utilizing government support and effective marketing strategies indicates that collaboration between educational institutions and stakeholders is essential to support the sustainability and growth of madrasahs. The government is expected to pay more attention to madrasahs that strive to innovate in order to provide more adequate facilities and training. This transformation model can be adopted as a reference in designing development programs for madrasahs throughout Indonesia, so that Islamic education can continue to compete and adapt to the times.

The transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan has faced several significant challenges, particularly in adapting educators to the new system, which requires additional skills. One of the primary difficulties lies in training teachers to effectively use technology, especially in computer labs. MIG1 noted, “We still have difficulty operating some of the devices in the lab, so training is very necessary.” Beyond technology, there is also a challenge in developing skills related to teaching foreign languages, which are part of this transformation. MIG3 stated, “Without further training, it is difficult for us to keep up with the developments needed.” This sentiment was echoed by MIG4, who emphasized that the success of the management transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan would largely depend on the readiness of educators to implement changes comprehensively. Therefore, ongoing training is an essential aspect that the madrasah must prioritize to ensure educators are well-equipped to provide optimal education.

In addition to challenges with teacher readiness, budget constraints also pose a significant hurdle in developing adequate learning facilities. Although MIN 1 Grobogan receives support from the Ministry of Religious Affairs, the school still struggles to meet the need for more sophisticated equipment. MIG5 admitted, “The existing budget is not enough to buy the sophisticated devices we need.” MIG7 added, “Some computers are old and require expensive maintenance.” According to MIG2, maintaining these facilities often strains the limited budget, making it clear that further support is necessary. MIG4 emphasized that collaboration from the government, the

community, and other stakeholders would greatly assist the sustainability of this transformation. This challenge underscores the importance of cooperation among various parties to ensure that MIN 1 Grobogan can continue its transformation and enhance the quality of education.

The management transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan has had a profound impact, not only on the madrasah but also on the broader Islamic education system in Indonesia. The school's success in attracting public interest through management innovation demonstrates that madrasahs can offer high-quality education on par with public schools. MIG1 remarked, "MIN 1 Grobogan proves that with innovation, madrasahs can attract more students." By consistently strengthening Islamic values while incorporating modern skills, MIN 1 Grobogan has become a model for other madrasahs. MIG2 added, "This new approach has increased public trust in madrasahs." The transformation serves as an inspiration for other Islamic educational institutions to adopt similar strategies to enhance their competitiveness. MIG4 reinforced this idea, stating, "Innovation in management is very important to improve the quality of education in madrasahs." MIN 1 Grobogan has thus established a new paradigm, showing that madrasahs have the potential to compete in the broader educational landscape.

From an educational management perspective, the transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan illustrates how adaptation to contemporary needs can be achieved without compromising religious values. MIG3 observed, "The combination of religious activities with 21st-century skills is the key to the success of madrasahs." By blending religious teachings with skills like foreign languages and technology, MIN 1 Grobogan has created an Islamic education model that aligns with global demands. MIG5 added, "A holistic education creates graduates who are ready to face global challenges." This approach suggests that the development of madrasahs requires not only changes in teaching methods but also innovations in governance. MIG7 commented, "Modern facilities and relevant methods are essential to meet the expectations of today's society." The transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan has not only advanced teaching methods but also bolstered the position of madrasahs as educational institutions ready to thrive in the modern world.

Finally, the transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan carries positive implications for the development of Islamic education policies at both regional and national levels. The school's success in utilizing government support and effective marketing strategies demonstrates that collaboration between educational institutions and stakeholders is crucial for sustaining and growing madrasahs. It is expected that the government will continue to support madrasahs that are committed to innovation by providing more adequate facilities and training. This transformation model can serve as a reference for designing development programs for madrasahs across Indonesia, ensuring that Islamic education can continue to adapt and compete in the contemporary educational environment.

5. Discussion

This research reveals that MIN 1 Grobogan has successfully implemented a strategy for transforming madrasah management and increasing public trust through various strategic efforts. First, the madrasah focuses on building an innovative and quality image by promoting excellent programs in academic and non-academic fields, attracting public interest in entrusting their children's education in addition to mastering soft skills through extracurricular activities. Second, transparent fund management creates public trust, supported by accountability in the use of operational funds. Third, friendly and professional service is the advantage of the madrasah, with staff providing the best service for students and guardians. Improving the quality of teachers through ongoing training is also prioritized, including the use of information technology in the teaching and learning process. The madrasah integrates religious values and social skills through daily habituation programs, so that students not only excel academically but also have strong characters. In addition, cooperation with the local community is strengthened by involving parents and community leaders in various activities. Although this strategy has succeeded in increasing public trust in MIN 1 Grobogan as a transparent and quality educational institution, this transformation faces challenges, including the adaptation of educators to the new system that requires additional skills and budget constraints for the development of adequate learning facilities.

Henry Mintzberg and Peter Drucker's views in the context of research on management transformation strategies at MIN 1 Grobogan reflect the importance of effective leadership and innovative managerial approaches in increasing public trust. Mintzberg (1989) emphasized that a flexible and team-oriented organizational structure can encourage collaboration and creativity, which is in line with the madrasah's efforts to develop an innovative image through excellent programs in academic and non-academic fields. On the other hand, Drucker (2006) emphasized that the goal of educational management must focus on the results and value generated for the community, which is seen in the madrasah's efforts to manage funds transparently and accountably, so as to increase public trust. Friendly and professional service, which is the advantage of the madrasah, also reflects Drucker's principle of the importance of customer orientation, namely students and guardians. In this context, improving teacher quality through continuous training and integration of religious values and social skills is a strategic step that supports the madrasah's vision to produce students with strong character (Drucker, 2006). However, the challenges in this transformation, such as the adaptation of educational staff to the new system and budget constraints, indicate the need for a managerial approach that is adaptive and responsive to change, in line with Mintzberg's thinking (Mintzberg & Laasch, 2020) regarding the importance of managers as directors who are able to deal with the dynamics of the educational environment.

The novelty of this research finding lies in the integration of contemporary management theories put forward by Henry Mintzberg and Peter Drucker with pre-existing Islamic principles. While Islamic theories emphasize values such as justice, transparency, and social responsibility, this research shows how both views can complement each other in the context of management transformation strategies at MIN 1 Grobogan. Mintzberg's approach that emphasizes organizational flexibility and team collaboration, as well as Drucker's emphasis on outcomes that provide value to society, can be adapted to strengthen Islamic principles that emphasize the importance of morality in education. This research also highlights how madrasahs implement continuous training for teachers, which not only focuses on professional development but also integrates religious values and social skills, creating students with character (Adelia & Mitra, 2021). In addition, challenges in implementing transformation strategies, such as teacher adaptation to new systems and budget constraints, emphasize the need for adaptive management. These findings suggest that modern management theories with Islamic values can produce a more holistic approach to education, which is able to answer contemporary challenges and increase public trust in educational institutions (Alawiyah, 2014). Thus, this research not only enriches the discourse on educational management, but also provides new insights into the application of Islamic values in a broader context.

This research reflects the importance of the role of Islamic identity and modern innovation in the management of Islamic education. At the beginning of the transformation, MIN 1 Grobogan attempted to improve deficiencies in several fundamental aspects, such as the schedule structure, uniforms, and religious habits. Over time, the results showed that these efforts not only improved student discipline but also strengthened the image of the madrasah as an educational institution that is consistent with Islamic values. In the final stage of the transformation, the addition of foreign language facilities and information technology became important elements that provided added value to the madrasah. This shows that the combination of managerial innovation and religious values is an attraction that is able to distinguish MIN Kuwaron from the surrounding public schools.

The interpretation of the results of this research emphasizes the importance of flexibility in educational management, where adaptation to modern demands does not have to ignore the religious values that are the foundation of madrasahs. Strengthening religious activities such as reading *Asmaul Husna*, *tadarus*, *tahlil*, and *surah yasin*, as well as the application of information technology at MIN 1 Grobogan, shows that Islamic education can remain relevant to the times without losing its identity. These results provide empirical evidence that the management of Islamic education that is responsive to the needs of the times and consistent with Islamic values can increase public appeal. Thus, the model applied at MIN 1 Grobogan has an important meaning in showing that madrasahs have great potential to compete with public schools if managed adaptively.

Comparatively, the research conducted by (Azra, 2001; Munadi, Alwiyah, et al., 2021; Munadi, Annur, et al., 2021; Munadi & Khuriyah, 2023; Nata, 2003) shows that adaptive management transformation can increase the competitiveness of Islamic education amidst the dominance of general education and intracurricular and co-curricular education. Nata highlights the importance of innovation in curriculum and management to face global

challenges, while Azra emphasizes the role of strong religious identity as the main attraction in Islamic education. Munadi et al. emphasize the development of extracurricular activities to strengthen soft skills in addition to hard skills. This research strengthens this view by providing a real example from MIN 1 Grobogan, where the combination of managerial innovation and daily religious activities forms a madrasah that is relevant and in demand by the community. The novelty of this research is the emphasis on the implementation of intensive marketing strategies as a way to strengthen the image of the madrasah, which is rarely discussed in other Islamic education research.

As a future action plan, MIN 1 Grobogan can continue to develop its managerial innovation by paying attention to three main areas: (1) developing teacher competencies, improving technological facilities, and maintaining religious identity. Continuous training for teachers in foreign language skills and technology will improve the quality of education and the sustainability of the programs that have been pioneered. (2) Improving technological facilities, such as updating computer equipment, will support digital learning programs that are increasingly relevant in this era. On the other hand, to maintain Islamic appeal, (3) MIN 1 Grobogan can enrich daily religious activities with Al-Qur'an memorization programs or Islamic etiquette training, so that students not only have modern skills but also strong Islamic characters. This action plan will ensure that the management transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan can continue and be an inspiration for other madrasahs in Indonesia.

This research reveals that MIN 1 Grobogan has successfully implemented a strategy for transforming madrasah management and increasing public trust through various strategic efforts. First, the madrasah focuses on building an innovative and high-quality image by promoting excellent programs in both academic and non-academic fields. This approach attracts public interest in entrusting their children's education to the institution while also helping students master soft skills through extracurricular activities. Second, transparent fund management fosters public trust, supported by accountability in the use of operational funds. Third, the madrasah's friendly and professional service is one of its key advantages, with staff providing excellent service to students and parents. Improving the quality of teachers through ongoing training is also a priority, including enhancing their use of information technology in the teaching and learning process. The madrasah integrates religious values and social skills through daily habituation programs, ensuring that students not only excel academically but also develop strong character. In addition, cooperation with the local community is strengthened by involving parents and community leaders in various activities. Although this strategy has been successful in increasing public trust in MIN 1 Grobogan as a transparent and high-quality educational institution, the transformation faces challenges. These include the adaptation of educators to the new system, which requires additional skills, as well as budget constraints in developing adequate learning facilities.

Henry Mintzberg and Peter Drucker's views, in the context of research on management transformation strategies at MIN 1 Grobogan, highlight the importance of effective leadership and innovative managerial approaches in building public trust. Mintzberg (1989) emphasized that a flexible, team-oriented organizational structure fosters collaboration and creativity, which aligns with the madrasah's efforts to develop an innovative image through excellent academic and non-academic programs. On the other hand, Drucker (2006) argued that the goal of educational management should focus on the results and value generated for the community, which is reflected in the madrasah's transparent and accountable fund management to enhance public trust. The madrasah's friendly and professional service, which is one of its key advantages, also reflects Drucker's principle of customer orientation, which prioritizes students and guardians. In this context, improving teacher quality through continuous training and the integration of religious values and social skills are strategic steps that support the madrasah's vision of producing students with strong character. However, the challenges in this transformation, such as the adaptation of educational staff to the new system and budget constraints, highlight the need for a managerial approach that is adaptive and responsive to change. This aligns with Mintzberg's thinking (Mintzberg & Laasch, 2020) about the role of managers as directors who must navigate the dynamics of the educational environment.

The novelty of this research lies in the integration of contemporary management theories proposed by Henry Mintzberg and Peter Drucker with traditional Islamic principles. While Islamic theories emphasize values such as justice, transparency, and social responsibility, this research demonstrates how both perspectives can complement each other in the context of management transformation strategies at MIN 1 Grobogan. Mintzberg's approach,

which emphasizes organizational flexibility and team collaboration, along with Drucker's focus on outcomes that provide value to society, can be adapted to strengthen Islamic principles that underscore the importance of morality in education. This research also highlights how madrasahs implement continuous training for teachers, which not only focuses on professional development but also integrates religious values and social skills, ultimately shaping students with strong character (Adelia & Mitra, 2021). Moreover, challenges in implementing transformation strategies—such as teacher adaptation to new systems and budget constraints—underscore the need for adaptive management. These findings suggest that combining modern management theories with Islamic values offers a more holistic approach to education, one that can address contemporary challenges and enhance public trust in educational institutions (Alawiyah, 2014). Thus, this research not only enriches the discourse on educational management, but also provides new insights into the application of Islamic values in a broader context.

This research underscores the importance of combining Islamic identity and modern innovation in the management of Islamic education. At the beginning of the transformation, MIN 1 Grobogan focused on addressing deficiencies in several key areas, such as scheduling, uniforms, and religious practices. Over time, these efforts not only improved student discipline but also strengthened the madrasah's image as an institution aligned with Islamic values. In the final phase of the transformation, the introduction of foreign language facilities and information technology became crucial elements that added significant value to the madrasah. This demonstrates that the integration of managerial innovation with religious values is a distinguishing factor that sets MIN 1 Grobogan apart from surrounding public schools.

The interpretation of the results emphasizes the importance of flexibility in educational management. Adaptation to modern demands does not have to come at the expense of the religious values that form the foundation of madrasahs. Strengthening religious activities such as reading *Asmaul Husna*, *tadarus*, *tahlil*, and *Surah Yasin*, alongside the integration of information technology at MIN 1 Grobogan, shows that Islamic education can remain relevant without losing its identity. These findings provide empirical evidence that Islamic education management, responsive to contemporary needs while remaining consistent with Islamic values, can significantly increase public appeal. Thus, the model applied at MIN 1 Grobogan serves as an important example, demonstrating that madrasahs have great potential to compete with public schools when managed adaptively.

In comparison, research conducted by (Azra, 2001; Munadi, Alwiyah, et al., 2021; Munadi, Annur, et al., 2021; Munadi & Khuriyah, 2023; Nata, 2003) shows that adaptive management transformation can enhance the competitiveness of Islamic education in the face of the dominance of general education and both intracurricular and co-curricular activities. Nata emphasizes the role of innovation in curriculum and management to meet global challenges, while Azra highlights the significance of maintaining a strong religious identity as a key attraction in Islamic education. Munadi et al. stress the importance of developing extracurricular activities to strengthen soft skills alongside hard skills. This research reinforces these perspectives by offering a practical example from MIN 1 Grobogan, where the combination of managerial innovation and daily religious activities creates a madrasah that remains relevant and in demand by the community. The novelty of this research lies in its focus on the implementation of intensive marketing strategies as a means to strengthen the madrasah's image—an approach rarely discussed in other studies on Islamic education.

For future action, MIN 1 Grobogan can continue to develop its managerial innovations by focusing on three main areas: (1) developing teacher competencies, improving technological facilities, and maintaining religious identity. Continuous training in foreign language skills and technology will enhance the quality of education and the sustainability of the programs already introduced. (2) Improving technological facilities, such as updating computer equipment, will support the digital learning programs that are increasingly relevant today. Meanwhile, to maintain its Islamic appeal, (3) MIN 1 Grobogan can enrich its daily religious activities with *Al-Qur'an* memorization programs or Islamic etiquette training, ensuring that students not only acquire modern skills but also cultivate strong Islamic character. This action plan will ensure that the management transformation at MIN 1 Grobogan continues to progress and serves as an inspiration for other madrasahs across Indonesia.

6. Conclusion

This research offers a new perspective on how management transformation in madrasahs can enhance competitiveness and public trust. One of its significant contributions is the emphasis on combining religious identity with modern innovation in Islamic education. By integrating Islamic learning programs with foreign language skills and technology, MIN 1 Grobogan provides a practical example of how madrasahs can be adaptive educational institutions without compromising religious values. This research also contributes to the literature on Islamic education management by highlighting intensive marketing strategies as a key element in shaping a positive image of madrasahs, an aspect rarely addressed in previous studies. Another important finding is the role of daily religious programs in strengthening the institution's identity. These programs not only enhance students' connection to Islamic values but also distinguish the madrasah from public schools. In this context, MIN 1 Grobogan has successfully combined modern innovation with religious practices, demonstrating that consistent Islamic elements in students' daily lives can be a unique attraction for the community. Therefore, this research provides practical recommendations for other madrasahs seeking to improve their educational quality, while also contributing to the development of a more holistic theory of Islamic educational management that considers the interplay between religious and modern elements in creating competitive educational institutions.

However, the main limitation of this research is its approach, which focuses on a single school through a case study design. While this provides in-depth insights into the specific context and conditions of MIN 1 Grobogan, it limits the generalizability of the findings to other madrasahs, which may have different characteristics and challenges. Moreover, focusing on one location may overlook external factors influencing management transformation and public trust, such as national education policies and the social dynamics of the surrounding community. For future research, it is recommended to include multiple madrasahs from various regions to offer a more comprehensive understanding of the broader trends in madrasah management transformation. Integrating quantitative methods would help collect broader, more representative data, enabling a deeper analysis of the relationship between madrasah management and public trust. Additionally, employing a mixed-methods approach—combining qualitative and quantitative research—could reveal other influencing variables and provide stronger recommendations for madrasah management development policies in Indonesia.

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